

Valorization of oil and fats and food waste to improve co-digestion performance

Deliverable 2.2

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Summary

Deliverable 2.2 is a technical report on the work carried out in Task 2.1 within the Alicante Living Lab, more specifically in subtask 2.1.1 that had the objective of developing, customizing and demonstrating a pilot scale validation of the valorisation of oil & fats from wastewater and food waste from other industries, aiming at improving co-digestion performance and producing biogas from sewage sludge.

The present report gives a brief introduction to the current operation of the on-site digesters at Rincón de León WWTP. It then characterizes the co-substrates used for the piloting campaign. The piloting campaign is explained, and the pilot plant is presented, as well as the retrofitting work completed. The results of the campaign are shown and discussed, as well as the potential environmental and economical benefits of the full-scale implementation of the co-digestion of the residues in the WWTP Anaerobic Digestion process.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

AD - Anaerobic Digestion

AcoD - Anaerobic Co-digestion

BMP - Biochemical methane potential

CAD - Computer-Aided Design

CAPEX - Capital Expenditure

CAS - Conventional Activated Sludge

CHP - Combined Heat and Power

COD - Chemical Oxygen Demand

EI - Expected Impact

HMI - Human Machine Interface

HRT – Hydraulic Retention Time

LL - Living Lab

MO - Monte Orgegia

N – Nitrogen

NTK – Nitrogen Total Kjeldahl

OLR - Organic Loading Rate

OPEX - Operational Expenditure

P - Phosphorus

PLC - Programmable Logic Controller

RdL - Rincón de León

PFAS - Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances

PPCP - Pharmaceuticals and Personal Care Products

SS - Sewage Sludge

TN - Total Nitrogen

TP - Total Phosphorus

TRL - Technology readiness Level

TS - Total Solids

TSS - Total Suspended Solids

VS - Volatile Solids

VSS - Volatile Suspended Solids

WWTP – Wastewater Treatment Plant

Revision history

The table below provides detailed explanations of the integration of the changes requested as part of the final project review.

Feedback received	How the feedback has been integrated in D2.2
<p>Please elaborate the handling of the residues of the co-digestion. How were they treated and disposed of? How did the quality change (e.g. dewaterability, quality, legal implications e.g. for land application, etc.)</p>	<p>A new subsection, 8.1 Waste management and handling, has been included in the reviewed D2.2 to address the feedback received.</p>
<p>Please discuss particularly the pollution aspect of sewage sludge and how relevant the contamination with persistent pollutants such as PFAS, heavy metals, organic micropollutants is towards reaching circularity when producing these mixed residual solids. Several countries are hesitant to mixing food waste with sewage due to the pollution issue.</p>	<p>A new section 9. Considerations in sludge pollution for agriculture has been included in the reviewed D2.2 to address the feedback received.</p>

Executive summary

D2.2 represents a comprehensive technical report that integrates the efforts conducted within the scope of subtask 2.1.1, focusing on the co-digestion of sewage sludge and diverse co-substrates at the Rincón de León WWTP in Alicante Living Lab. The document starts by introducing the fundamentals of anaerobic digestion (AD) and underscores the advantages of co-digestion. By combining sewage sludge with various organic materials, co-digestion may mitigate the limitations associated with the digestion of sludge alone, thereby enhancing overall process efficiency and biogas yield, among other advantages.

The subsequent sections provide a summarised and graphical overview of the whole completed phases of this technology at the site in Alicante, setting the groundwork for the shift from mono-digestion to co-digestion of sewage sludge and waste. Multiple potential co-substrates, including oil & fats and food waste, were identified. The report details the physico-chemical characterization, methane production and biodegradability potential of both sewage sludge and the identified waste materials. Notably, an ice-cream waste sourced from a local industry emerged as a promising candidate for co-digestion, offering significant potential to increase biogas production.

A dedicated section outlines the demonstration phases of the pilot plant, operating under continuous regime conditions. The initial phase involved the digestion of sewage sludge alone, establishing a baseline and achieving comparable values to the existing digester at the Rincón de León WWTP. Subsequently, a 5% (v/v - volume) introduction of cream waste into the pilot reactor for co-digestion was executed and later on a similar approach was adopted with another co-substrate, based on fruit and vegetable waste sourced from another local industry. The resulting biogas yield increase is addressed and discussed, as well as the observed synergy and lack of inhibition.

Given the promising results obtained, especially with the cream waste, a final section is incorporated envisioning the full-scale implementation and the expected outcomes in terms of biogas production translated into electricity production capacity and thus energy savings from its valorisation at Rincón de León WWTP, as well as GHG emissions abatement.

In the last section, conclusions of the piloting campaign and data analysis are summarised and next steps for the technology and implementation in the site are drafted. The impact achieved is also included at the end of the present document together with technical requirements and specifications for co-digestion implementation.

1 Introduction

1.1 Anaerobic co-digestion

Anaerobic digestion (AD) is a natural biological process that breaks down organic matter in the absence of oxygen. It is a sustainable and environmentally friendly method of treating organic waste, such as agricultural residues, food scraps, and sewage sludge, to produce biogas (a renewable gas composed of mostly CO₂ and CH₄) and nutrient-rich digestate.

During AD, microorganisms break down the organic material through a series of biological reactions (Figure 1.1), producing methane-rich biogas as a byproduct. This biogas can be used as a renewable energy source for heat and electricity generation or upgraded for use as biomethane which can be injected in the gas network, used as fuel for vehicles, while the remaining digestate serves as a valuable fertilizer. The main steps involved in anaerobic digestion are the following:

- **Hydrolysis:** In the first stage, complex organic compounds in the feedstock are broken down into simpler compounds through hydrolysis. This process involves the action of enzymes that break down large molecules into smaller ones, such as sugars, amino acids, and fatty acids.
- **Acidogenesis:** The simpler compounds produced during hydrolysis are then converted into organic acids through acidogenesis. Acid-forming bacteria facilitate this stage by fermenting the products of hydrolysis.
- **Acetogenesis:** Organic acids are further broken down into acetic acid, hydrogen, and carbon dioxide through acetogenesis. Acetogenic bacteria play a key role in this stage.
- **Methanogenesis:** In the final stage, methane is produced through methanogenesis. Methanogenic archaea convert the acetic acid, hydrogen, and carbon dioxide generated in previous stages into methane and carbon dioxide. Methane is the primary component of biogas.

Figure 1.1 Anaerobic digestion process and reaction steps (Source: Bajpai, P. (2017))

AD does not only help in waste management by reducing the volume of organic waste but also contributes to the production of clean energy and nutrient-rich soil amendments. It plays a crucial role in sustainable waste management practices and contributes to the circular economy by turning waste into valuable resources.

1.2 Anaerobic co-digestion

In the ever-evolving landscape of renewable energy and sustainable waste management, anaerobic co-digestion (AcoD) stands out as a pivotal and innovative process within the sector of biogas production. Anaerobic co-digestion is a technology that has garnered increasing attention and recognition for its ability to not only generate renewable energy but also address multiple environmental and waste management challenges. AcoD involves the simultaneous digestion of multiple organic feedstocks in anaerobic digesters, with the aim of harnessing the synergistic benefits that arise from combining various materials. This approach has expanded the scope of biogas production beyond traditional agricultural substrates, enabling a broader range of organic waste streams, such as food waste, sewage sludge, and industrial byproducts, to be utilized as valuable resources in the production of biogas.

Additionally, anaerobic co-digestion aligns with the principles of the circular economy by transforming organic waste materials into renewable energy and nutrient-rich digestate. As governments and industries worldwide seek to reduce their carbon footprint, reduce energy dependency and adopt more sustainable practices, AcoD has gained momentum, supported by favourable policies, incentives, and funding mechanisms that promote its adoption.

1.3 State of the art

The state-of-the-art in anaerobic co-digestion represents a confluence of technological advancements, environmental imperatives, and economic incentives, making it a compelling solution in the quest for cleaner and more efficient energy generation.

Key developments in anaerobic co-digestion include the optimization of feedstock combinations to enhance methane production, the refinement of digester technologies to improve process efficiency and stability, and the integration of advanced monitoring and control systems for precise management of the digestion process. Moreover, the environmental benefits of anaerobic co-digestion are increasingly recognized, including the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions through the capture of methane, as well as the mitigation of odour and pathogens in organic waste streams.

The assessment of co-substrates plays a crucial role in unveiling synergistic interactions among different feedstocks, potentially enhancing the overall efficiency of biogas production. By scrutinizing the compatibility and performance of co-substrates, researchers and practitioners contribute to the advancement of anaerobic co-digestion technology, fostering a more resilient and resource-efficient approach to waste-to-energy conversion. While numerous studies have been conducted to assess the potential of different substrates in co-digestion scenarios (Azarmanesh et al., 2023), it is paramount to recognize the intrinsic variability among these materials. Each substrate possesses unique characteristics, such as biochemical composition, nutrient content, and degradation rates, which can significantly impact the overall performance of anaerobic digestion. Therefore, the innovation lies not only in exploring co-digestion but also in meticulously evaluating each substrate. This focused assessment is imperative to discern the individual nuances of substrates, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of their behavior in anaerobic environments.

However, it's essential to note that research and innovation in the field of anaerobic co-digestion continue to evolve rapidly. New technologies, feedstock combinations, and operational strategies are continuously emerging, driving the efficiency and sustainability of biogas production through co-digestion to new heights. This state-of-the-art technology is not only a promising avenue for renewable energy generation but also a critical component in the transition towards a greener and more circular economy.

1.4 Mono- vs co-digestion

Anaerobic digestion of sewage sludge alone can be a viable waste management and energy generation option, but it does have several drawbacks when compared to anaerobic co-digestion, which involves the simultaneous digestion of multiple organic feedstocks. Some of the main drawbacks of anaerobic digestion of sewage sludge alone include:

- **Lower Methane Yield:** Sewage sludge typically has a lower methane yield compared to some other organic feedstocks, such as agricultural residues or dedicated energy crops. This

means that when sewage sludge is digested alone, the biogas production and subsequent energy output may be relatively low.

- **Imbalance in Nutrient Content:** Sewage sludge tends to have an imbalanced nutrient content, particularly high levels of nitrogen and phosphorus. This can lead to suboptimal conditions for the microbes involved in anaerobic digestion and may require additional treatments or adjustments to maintain stable digestion.
- **Variable Characteristics:** The composition of sewage sludge can vary significantly depending on the source and treatment processes. This variability can make it challenging to predict and optimize the anaerobic digestion process when sewage sludge is used as the sole feedstock.
- **Digestate Quality:** The digestate produced from sewage sludge digestion may have limited agricultural value due to its high heavy metal content and potential presence of pathogens and pharmaceutical residues. This can restrict its use as a beneficial soil conditioner or fertilizer.
- **Odour and Pathogen Concerns:** Sewage sludge can produce unpleasant odours during digestion, which can be a concern for nearby communities. Additionally, pathogen reduction may be less effective when sewage sludge is digested alone (Karki et al., 2021), potentially posing health risks

In contrast, anaerobic co-digestion addresses many of these drawbacks by blending sewage sludge with other organic materials. Co-digestion can enhance the overall process efficiency and biogas yield in several ways:

- **Balanced Nutrient Mix:** Mixing sewage sludge with other feedstocks can create improved balanced nutrient mix, which is beneficial for microbial activity and digestion stability.
- **Increased Methane Production:** Co-digestion allows for the use of feedstocks with higher methane potential, leading to increased biogas production and energy generation.
- **Improved Digestate Quality:** The addition of other feedstocks can improve the quality of the digestate, making it more suitable for agricultural use and reducing concerns about heavy metals and pathogens.
- **Dilution of Inhibitors:** Co-digestion can help dilute potential inhibitors present in sewage sludge, promoting a more efficient and stable digestion process.
- **Economic Viability:** Co-digestion can enhance the economic viability of biogas facilities by diversifying feedstock sources and potentially attracting additional revenue streams.

2 Context in Rincón de León WWTP

The Rincón de León wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) is one of the three treatment plants located in the Spanish municipality of Alicante. The Rincón de León WWTP serves a large part of the urban area of Alicante and the municipality of San Vicente del Raspeig. It has the capacity to purify 75,000 m³ of wastewater per day. Wastewater treatment is carried out by activated sludge and anaerobic digestion and has two treatment lines. The company in charge of its exploitation is Aguas de Alicante (AMAEM). The following Table 2.1 includes the main parameters of the plant.

Table 2.1 Main figures of Rincón de León WWTP

Design capacity (m³/day)	75,000
Equivalent population (PE)	562,500
Mean treated flow (m³/day)	48,627
Served population (PE)	285,719
Treatment units: water line	Conventional activated sludge (CAS), tertiary treatment, disinfection
Treatment units: sludge line	Anaerobic digestion, Dehydration, Cogeneration

On the other hand, the main parameters related to the anaerobic digestion currently in the WWTP are shown in Table 2.2.

Table 2.2 AD parameters in Rincón de León WWTP

Number of digesters (#)	4 (2 operative)
Capacity of digestion (m³)	16,000 (10,000 operative)
Sludge feed flow (m³/d)	500
Biogas production (Nm³/y)	1,092,514
Methane concentration (%)	67
Electricity generated (GWhe/year)	2.1

The energy recovery from biogas valorisation in RdL WWTP is rather low due to old infrastructure and limited process capacity. For this reason, Aguas de Alicante is willing to update the whole system and is also looking for ways to improve and maximise biogas production, which is why anaerobic co-digestion has been selected to assess its efficiency.

3 Identification and characterization of co-substrates

3.1 Oil & fats

In addition to the generation of sewage sludge as a by-product of the wastewater treatment process, the Rincón de León WWTP produces a specific solid waste stream referred to as Oil&Fats. Currently, the management of this waste stream is outsourced to external entities. The "oil&fats" residue originates from the supernatant extracted from the degreaser unit before it undergoes further treatment in the primary settler.

This particular waste stream represents a unique challenge in the overall waste management system of the WWTP. Comprising residual substances from the degreaser unit, the Oil&Fats component requires specialized attention due to its distinct chemical composition and characteristics. Efficient management and disposal strategies for this waste stream are crucial not only to ensure compliance with environmental regulations but also to optimise the overall operational efficiency of the wastewater treatment facility.

As the supernatant from the degreaser unit is a precursor to the primary settler, understanding and addressing the specific properties of the Oil&Fats residue becomes integral to enhancing the overall performance and sustainability of the wastewater treatment process. This underscores the importance of developing in-house strategies or collaborating with specialised waste management partners to handle and treat the Oil&Fats waste stream in an environmentally responsible and economically viable manner.

Figure 3.1 Photos of the oil&fats waste stream in Rincón de León WWTP

A characterization of these residues was carried out to assess its potential as a co-substrate for anaerobic digestion towards the improvement of biogas production. The total annual production of this waste stream is of only 8 Tn/y, which even in the case that it had a very good potential biogas production per ton, it would still not place it as a good candidate for co-digestion, as the total biogas production would not be significant.

Moreover, it is significantly composed of non-biodegradable matter (cotton swabs, wipes, small plastics etc), which is not prone to produce biogas. To further support this last statement, in the characterization the Volatile Suspended Solids (VSS) content were also analysed, which can be a reliable parameter to predict the organic matter that could potentially transform into biogas. The Volatile Solids (VS) content in this co-substrate was 2.8 g/L, whereas for the sewage sludge it was 19.8 g VS/L.

As the analysis of the oil&fats waste failed to yield encouraging results for enhancing biogas generation (i.e. 2.8 g VS/L), a comprehensive local research action was undertaken. This effort aimed to identify industries within the vicinity that might produce compatible waste streams suitable for incorporation as co-substrates in AD.

The outreach involved proposing the integration of the ongoing study and assessing the industries' interest in participating by contributing with their waste streams. By initiating these communications, collaborative partnerships that could potentially enhance biogas production capabilities were fostered. This strategic approach not only aimed to broaden the spectrum of waste inputs for enhanced biogas yield but also sparked a spirit of cooperation among local industries towards sustainable waste management practices.

3.2 Cream waste from Ice-cream industry

The first company that showed interest in collaborating with the project was a local company that produces artisan ice-cream and generates more than 290 Tn/year of a creamy waste (Figure 3.2). This waste is currently externally managed and the production plant is located near from the Rincón de León WWTP.

Figure 3.2 Cream waste

Figure 3.3 shows the evolution of the cream waste production during the years 2018, 2019 and 2020. As it can be seen, its production greatly fluctuates in a seasonal manner, which can be easily explained as ice-cream is mostly consumed and thus produced during warmer months.

Figure 3.3 Cream waste production 2018 to 2020

The industry has an industrial WWTP at their facilities to treat their wastewater before discharging them. As a result of the biological treatment provided to the water, a sludge is produced, as in a conventional activated sludge treatment. This sludge is partially dried and managed externally. Given its nature, this waste has also been considered as potential co-substrate for co-digestion and will be later assessed in terms of biogas potential in the present document.

3.3 Fruit waste from fruit and vegetable industry

A local fruit and vegetable industry also showed interest in the collaboration with B-WaterSmart and Alicante LL. Located near Rincón de León WWTP, it is the food unit of the city of Alicante feeding more than 1.9 million inhabitants and generates more than 700 Tn/year of solid urban waste that consists of fruits and vegetables, and is currently managed externally as waste.

The type of waste that is generated in its facilities can be seen in Figure 3.4. Since this waste consists of whole pieces of fruits and vegetables, a crushing process is necessary prior to its mixing with sewage sludge. The resulting crushed waste can be seen in the picture on the right in Figure 3.4.

Figure 3.4 Food waste before and after crushing

3.4 Characterization of wastes

The selected wastes were analysed in terms of pH, electrical conductivity, content of total solids (TS, g TS/L) and volatiles (VS, g VS/L) and total suspended solids (TSS, g TSS/kg) and volatile solids (SSV, g SSV/kg) in suspension, total and soluble organic matter content (chemical oxygen demand – COD, g O₂/L), total Kjeldahl nitrogen content (NTK, g N-NTK/L) and ammoniacal nitrogen (g N-NH₄⁺/L), total phosphorus content (g TP/L) and phosphate content (g P-PO₄³⁻/L). The analytical results obtained are summarised in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1. Physico-chemical characteristics of the identified wastes within B-WaterSmart. *Mixed sludge = mixture of sewage sludge from primary and secondary settlers

Parameter	Oil & fats	Mixed sludge*	Cream waste	Fruit waste
pH	7.1 ± 0.1	6.1 ± 0.2	4.2 ± 0.1	4.0 ± 0.2
Conductivity (mS/cm)	4.0 ± 0.0	5.8 ± 0.4	3.1 ± 1.2	4.8 ± 0.4
COD (g/L)	-	41.5 ± 2.2	528.0 ± 57.8	155.0 ± 61.8
Total Solids (g/L)	2.9 ± 0.1	30.3 ± 1.2	337.9 ± 53.7	124.4 ± 54.6
Volatile Solids (g/L)	2.8 ± 0.1	23.2 ± 0.9	330.0 ± 53.5	117.9 ± 54.2
VS/TS	0.99	0.77	0.98	0.95
COD/VS	-	1.79	1.60	1.31
Total N (g/L)	3.34 ± 3.82	0.48 ± 0.05	1.43 ± 0.49	0.96 ± 0.12
N-NH ₄ ⁺ (g/L)	0.19 ± 0.00	0.41 ± 0.05	0.10 ± 0.00	0.44
C/N ratio	-	1.23	64.68	20.49
Total P (g/L)	0.24 ± 0.01	0.10 ± 0.01	0.46 ± 0.10	0.17 ± 0.11
P-PO ₄ ²⁻ (g/L)	0.06 ± 0.00	0.08 ± 0.02	0.43 ± 0.15	0.15 ± 0.12

One of the most relevant indicators for the co-digestion potential of an organic waste is its Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD), which gives a first order of magnitude of the potential methane production. Although that analysis was inconclusive from Oil&Fats from the supernatant at Rincón de León, their low VS content indicates that COD will also be very low, much lower than the sludge itself (an order of magnitude lower), see Table 3.1.

On the other hand, the ice cream waste and the organic waste from fruit and vegetable unit have a very high COD, which indicates potential for co-digestion, although the biodegradability is yet to be tested. Another important parameter is the total solids content. The high solids content of ice cream waste would not be compatible with mono-digestion, as maximum total solids content would be around 150-200 g/L. However, in co-digestion the ice cream waste would be diluted with the sludge. The pH of the stream could also disrupt the AD process by lowering the pH of the anaerobic digester. The fruit waste and the ice cream waste might both inhibit AD digestion due to a low pH, which might need adjusting depending on the feeding rate in relation to sludge.

The ammonium concentration of cream waste and oil&fats is rather high, which could potentially inhibit the process if high concentrations of ammonium are reached within the anaerobic digester. Similarly, the high phosphorus (total and phosphate) could negatively impact the performance of AD. Ice cream waste has ammonium concentrations which might make it impossible to mono-digest

it. Nonetheless, the dilution factor in co-digestion should solve that issue. Phosphorus concentrations are greater than in Oil&Fats, this could also be a source of inhibition.

Noticeably, the fruit waste has a higher standard deviation than other co-substrates due to its varying nature. Visual observation of variability noted that occasionally a batch may consist of mono-crops while other batches had more variety, or consisted of spoiled vegetable crops.

The Carbon/Nitrogen (C/N) ratio of the mixed sludge is highly low in comparison with the other co-substrates. An ideal range of C/N ratio for anaerobic digestion would be between 20 and 40, which is reached by the cream waste and fruit waste. In this sense, mixing the mixed sludge with the co-substrated could optimize and increase this ratio. Overall, from Table 3.1 it can be stated that both fruit and ice cream waste seem to be potentially good candidates to co-digest with sludge due to their high CODs and counter balance sludges lower C/N and nutrient amounts, which might enable synergies in terms of COD removal and biogas production. Whereas Oil&Fats can be discarded due to their low VS content (and thus COD although not measured) and low volumetric availability.

3.5 Biochemical methane potential tests

Biochemical Methane Potential (BMP) tests are laboratory experiments designed to assess the potential for methane production from organic substrates under anaerobic conditions. Methane is a potent greenhouse gas, and its production is a key aspect of anaerobic digestion processes, for it is the component in biogas which gives it a heating value.

BMP tests are valuable tools in the field of bioenergy and waste management, providing essential data for the development of sustainable practices and technologies. They help researchers and practitioners understand the potential benefits and challenges associated with different organic materials in biogas production. The determination of the biogas production potential for the study's substrates was carried out through standardised tests for assessing the maximum biogas production potential and anaerobic biodegradability, following the VDI 4630 standard titled "Fermentation of organic materials". Figure 3.5 shows each substrate used for the tests: (1) Mixed sludge from Monte Orgegia WWTP, (2) Cream waste, (3) Mixed sludge from Rincón de León WWTP, (4) Crushed fruit waste and (5) sludge from the industrial WWTP in cream industry. For each substrate triplicate samples were assessed and with an inoculum blank at each batch to subtract methane production associated to the inoculum due to a residual presence of organic matter.

Figure 3.5 Picture of the substrates for BMP tests, from left to right: (1) Mixed sludge from Monte Orgegia WWTP, (2) Cream waste, (3) Mixed sludge from Rincón de León WWTP, (4) Crushed fruit waste and (5) sludge from the industrial WWTP in cream industry

Although technology #7 at B-WaterSmart is focused in the WWTP Rincón de León (3), it was decided to include sludge from the nearby WWTP Monte Orgegia (1) to extrapolate the results and potentially enable an additional future co-digestion location. It should be highlighted that the cream waste sludge (5) should not be confused with the ice cream waste (2). Although both come from the same facilities, their origin in the process is completely different, and so are their properties. The cream waste sludge (5) was not included in the characterization in Section 3.4 as it was determined that its flocculant behaviour would not be compatible with the co-digestion pilot plant, and as shown below in Figure 3.6, its BMP denotes low potential.

The BMPs for the five samples can be seen in Figure 3.6. The BMP was stopped once the biogas production was no longer significant, defined as a biogas production of less than 1% of the accumulated biogas in three days. The inoculum biogas production in the blank has already been subtracted from the raw biogas production and that is why at some points it seems like the accumulated biogas production decreases, which is not physically possible.

Figure 3.6 BMP tests for the five different substrates

As it can be seen, fruit (4) and cream waste (2) have a first quick biogas production ramp-up due to a fast degradation of the high-biodegradable organic fraction, but then stagnate until the inoculum adapts to the harder-to-degrade organic matter. Since this is a batch process whereas co-digestion will be continuous, the most important parameter is the final biogas production per kg of Volatile Solids and not the kinetics. Ice cream waste (2) and the mixed sludges (1) (3) have a similar production (685 and 698 NL/Kg VS, respectively) whereas fruit waste (4) has a slightly lower production per kg of VS. Ice cream sludge (5) has a much lower methane production (215 NL/Kg VS).

Although the measured variable from the BMPs is the totalized flow rate of biogas, the CO₂ in the biogas has no calorific value. Thus, the composition of the biogas was determined, so that the curves in Figure 3.6 can be translated to generated methane instead of biogas. See in Table 3.2 the final results for the five samples. Biodegradability is calculated from the methane production and the potential methane production if all COD was converted into CH₄, with a factor of 350 mL of CH₄ per gram of COD.

Table 3.2 BMP tests summarised results

Parameter	MO sludge (1)	Cream waste (2)	RdL sludge (3)	Fruit waste (4)	Cream sludge (5)
Methane (NL/Kg VS)	386	481	398	345	215
Biogas (NL/Kg VS)	685	733	698	559	333
Biodegradability (%)	-	85.9	63.5	75.0	-
CH ₄ (%)	56	66	57	62	65
H ₂ S (ppm)	391	964	522	342	582

It can be seen from Table 3.2 how the fruit and the ice cream waste show good biodegradability, with ice cream waste reaching 85.9%, similar to other co-substrates reported in the literature (Taboada-Santos et al., 2019) suitable for co-digestion.

4 Customization and commissioning of co-digestion pilot plant

The pilot plant used for co-digestion is an adaptation of an existing pilot plant from a past Research & Development project on co-digestion. Because the pilot plant had been decommissioned and out of use for a few years, it required some retrofitting, several maintenance actions as well as repairs and substitution of equipment parts. In section 4.1 a basic description of the pilot plant functionalities and equipment parts is given, whereas in section 4.2 the adaptations required so that the plant could be repurposed for the B-WaterSmart project are described.

In section 4.3 the experimental campaign on mono-digestion and co-digestion is addressed, and in section 4.4 the commissioning and start-up of the plant is explained. The results from the operational campaign can be found in chapter 5.

4.1 Basic description of the co-digestion pilot plant

The original pilot plant on co-digestion was designed and built in 2015 under the scope of the project COWARE, with private funding. The pilot plant was intended to test co-digestion mixtures of organic residues with WWTP sludge in a continuous manner, in order to test co-digestion in a real setting, being able to process real mixtures at non-optimal conditions and observe real biogas production, and quality, as well as find any potential bottlenecks or process inhibition, which cannot be detected at a BMP stage.

The pilot plant encompasses the following sub-processes:

- Sample pre-treatment, including mixing of co-substrates and crushing of solid organic waste with a motorized meat-mincing machine.
- Storage of co-substrate mixes for a buffer storage time of one week (730 L), with a cooling system to prevent degradation of the organic matter by keeping it at 4°C.
- Measurement of the volume of residues introduced into the digester by continuously measuring the weight of the digester, which is suspended in four digital scales.
- Digester level measurement and automatic control of the bleeding of digestate.
- Digester (1.600 L) mixing, temperature control and biogas drying and flaring.
- Monitoring of the digestion process: temperature, level, pH, conductivity and production (flow rate and composition) of biogas.
- Storage of digestate in a tank (100 L) with a hydraulic residence time of one day.

A schematic of the entire system and its control loops can be seen in Figure 4.1, a CAD drawing can be seen in Figure 4.2.

Figure 4.1 Simplified P&ID drawing of the pilot plant

Figure 4.2 CAD drawing of the side view of the pilot plant

4.2 Adaptation of pilot plant

The pilot plant was constructed in 2015 and was located at the Orense Wastewater Treatment Plant. After the experimentation was conducted in 2015, it was decommissioned. For the B-WaterSmart

project, it required some repairs and modifications. Auteima, the company entrusted with the refurbishment, undertook the following tasks:

- Replacement of the PLC and installation of a new HMI screen.
- Supply and installation of a new biogas flow meter.
- Supply and installation of a new pH probe.
- Supply and installation of an ATEX fan extractor.
- Supply and installation of a helical pump for sludge pumping to the digester.
- Replacement of the chiller control card.
- Logic control reform for digestion temperature control loop.
- Supply and installation of a new pressure probe for the digester.
- Supply and installation of an air conditioning unit.

Upon completion of these tasks, initial verification tests (Auteima-Cetaqua) were conducted, and the pilot plant was transferred to the facilities of Rincón de León WWTP in Alicante. When it was received at the site, the unloading, placement, and connection processes took place (see Figure 4.3).

Figure 4.3 Co-digestion plant being unloaded (left) and placed at its final location (right)

The established connections encompassed vital aspects such as potable water supply, the feed for mixed sludge, conduits for drainage, the provision of electrical power, and the implementation of general protective measures.

Recognizing the plant's aging state, attributed to the passage of time, a comprehensive rejuvenation effort was initiated. This involved not only meticulous cleaning procedures to enhance operational efficiency but also a meticulous finishing coat of paint to safeguard the plant's structural integrity. This dual approach aimed to not only address immediate functional requirements but also to contribute to the longevity and resilience of the facility in the face of ongoing operational demands and environmental conditions. The work completed can be seen below in Figure 4.4.

Figure 4.4 Interior of co-digestion plant before (left) and after (right) the cleanings and repairs

4.3 Experimental plan

After the customization of the pilot plan, an experimental plan was established to carry out the operation with the different substrates (see Table 4.1):

- Mono-digestion: anaerobic digestion of sewage sludge (SS) alone in order to set the baseline, which should meet similar values of biogas production and organic matter removal to those obtained in the WWTP full-scale digesters. 3 months were allocated for this task as anaerobic digestion start-ups take a long time to reach steady state.
- Co-digestion with creamy waste from cream industry.
- Co-digestion with fruit wastes from fruit unit.

Table 4.1 Experimental plan of the anaerobic co-digestion

	2022			2023											
	Oct	Nov	Des	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	July	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Des
Pilot transport, installation and connection															
Commissioning and start-up with water															
Mono-digestion with mixed SS*															
Co-digestion with cream waste + SS															
Co-digestion with fruit waste + SS															

*SS = Sewage sludge

4.4 Commissioning

During the commissioning of the co-digestion pilot plant several actions were undertaken:

- Firstly, the feed tank was filled with water. While the agitator operated correctly both manually and automatically, the chiller failed to start. The chiller malfunction was traced back to a poor connection in the electrical panel. It then operated temporarily after bridging its contactor. However, a permanent solution needed to be implemented, especially for automatic functionality. Furthermore, after a week of continuous operation, the chiller was unable to lower the temperature to the setpoint value (nor was it capable of decreasing by a few degrees daily). Consequently, it was advisable to contact a maintenance company for a thorough inspection, likely requiring a gas refill. This issue is addressed in section 4.5 Mono-digestion with sewage sludge.
- The weighing system of the feed tank was verified and found to be functioning correctly.
- The feed pump to the digester was started, but it was observed that it did not propel the liquid. It was identified that the pump was rotating in the opposite direction, indicating a phase reversal in the wiring. The issue was resolved by correcting the phases, and the pump was confirmed to function correctly in automatic mode (based on weight cycles) and manual mode.
- A flow measurement was conducted on the pump by measuring the pumped kilograms and time. The result indicated an approximate flow rate of 1 L/hour (appropriate).
- The digester was filled (about 20 cm away from surpassing the level of the sludge outlet pipe which was verified by unscrewing the conduit and visually inspecting, as the level sensor measurement was inaccurate).
- Similar to the level sensors, other instrumentation (pH sensors, conductivity, turbidity, pressure, temperature, etc.) faced the same challenge: the calibration ranges for the sensors were unknown. To obtain accurate measurements, these ranges had to be determined for each sensor.
- The operation of the digester agitator was correct in both automatic and manual modes. The frequency converter functioned properly.
- The sludge recirculation pump was started, but it was halted due to uncertainty about the level of sludge and to prevent dry operation.
- The automatic discharge valve operated correctly (both manually and automatically).
- The bottom drain valve of the digester was obstructed resulting in the digester emptying itself through leakage by gravity. It was disassembled, and remnants from past experiments were removed.
- The digester's heating element had a thermostat problem, causing it to stop heating the water at 45°C which is insufficient for proper sludge heating. The malfunction was repaired although the temperature was unknown due to the same sensor issue.

- The gas flow meter was received and installed. An analyzer was rented for measuring methane concentration in biogas, and the technician adjusted its configuration to be tested with the WWTP biogas.

4.5 Start-up

New actions undertaken to solve problems that arose during start-up:

- The chiller was replaced. The supply and installation of a semi-industrial machine with a power of 2 kW were subcontracted to ensure proper cooling of the feed tank to the digester to avoid degradation/digestion of the organic matter in the feeding tank. The new chiller can be seen in Figure 4.5.
- The temperature probe in the feed tank was prone to malfunction, leading to freezing of the sludge. A decision was made to install an external probe. This probe operates independently of the SCADA system and enables automatic equipment operation through its thermostat.

Figure 4.5 New chiller installed in the pilot plant

- A new waste shredder was acquired to process the fruit waste. This piece of equipment came with a start button, an emergency stop button, and its own small control and protection panel, see Figure 4.6.

Figure 4.6 Waste shredder/crusher

- The initial operational tests in mono-digestion with sludge from the Rincón de León WWTP were proven successful, with biogas generation occurring as soon as the pilot digester was filled with the WWTP inoculum. The initial feeding value for the digester was set at 44 kg/day, with a retention time of 25 days.
- Upon process initiation, biogas generation commenced, facilitating the calibration of the flowmeter for flow measurement. The average biogas flow stabilized at 0.7 L/min, achieving a COD removal efficiency close to 40%. The single digestion tests extended for over a month, maintaining an operational organic load of approximately 1.7 kg COD/m³.day. The produced biogas concentration reached values of 64% CH₄.
- The communication system was activated, and Auteima made necessary adjustments (gas totalizer, feeding sequence, valve extraction settings, etc.).

5 Operational results from experimental campaign

The operational campaign, as explained in section 4.3, was split in three-stages. First came the mono-digestion campaign, in which the SS from the WWTP was to be mono-digested to validate the functionality of the pilot plant and cross-check the results with the on-site digesters to validate the replicability. This validation comes mainly from the measurement of COD and VS elimination, as well as the measured biogas production (flow rate and concentration of methane). Once these parameters are comparable in unitary terms per m³ of SS to the existing digestion in Rincón de León WWTP, the co-digestion campaign can start.

The second stage consisted in digesting the SS with a 5% mix (in volume) of ice-cream waste and in the third stage the SS was digested in a 5% volume mix of fruit waste. This volume ratio is considered already very high given the available volumes of waste and the throughput of the digesters, and the implication on the Organic Loading Rate (OLR) and potential biogas production is much higher than a 5% increase.

Throughout the three stages there were punctual malfunctions of the pilot plant, which halted the process and required a re-inoculation with sewage sludge. These interruptions were due to different reasons, such as the freezing of the feeding tank due to a temperature sensor malfunction or the drop in SS feed to the digester due to a pump breakdown.

During the campaign, samples of the feeding SS co-substrate mix and digested sludge were taken to analyse its COD, TS and VS, as well as its nitrogen content. These parameters were not very consistent in the fed SS, presumably a consequence of the large difference in primary and secondary sludge characteristics of the WWTP and how these are fed in an uncontrolled manner to the site digester. Taking into account both (i) removed COD and (ii) the theoretical value of 350 mL CH₄/g COD, the methane production can be estimated. The resulting value can be compared with the measured biogas production within the pilot plant, from which both the biogas flow and methane content are monitored. In the coming sections describing the results from the operation of the pilot, single data points will not be considered representative, but the average values instead.

5.1 Mono-digestion campaign

The plant was started up with sewage sludge directly sampled from the on-site digesters. Since the entire volume of digester was filled with sewage sludge, the start-up of the digestion process was fast and did not require an adaptation period or inoculation time. The Hydraulic Retention Time (HRT) was set at 25 days. After a day, the pilot plant was producing biogas at the expected rate and composition (62-66 vol.%) given its feeding rate and volume. The plant was operated for two HRTs before the feed tank froze.

Figure 5.1 Pilot plant COD removal and biogas production (calculated and measured)

As seen in Figure 5.1 the biogas produced is in the same order of magnitude as estimated from the COD elimination. The data generated during the time period in which the feeding tank froze has not been included. The average measured biogas production was of 0.49 L/min whereas the average expected production would be of 0.33 L/min. This difference can be easily attributed to the low resolution of the biogas flow meter, and the fact that it is working on its lower range (it can measure up to 6.0 L/min, resolution of 0.1 L/min).

The biogas production per cubic meter of SS ($10.94 \text{ Nm}^3 \text{ biogas/m}^3 \text{ SS}$) is similar to that of the WWTP's on-site digesters ($10.86 \text{ Nm}^3 \text{ biogas/m}^3 \text{ SS}$), and the removal of COD is also similar, 48.2% in the pilot plant and 46.5% in the WWTP. It can then be stated that the pilot plant successfully replicated the on-site digesters at Rincón de León WWTP.

5.2 Co-digestion campaign with ice cream waste

Once the pilot plant mono-digestion had been validated, ice-cream waste was mixed with the SS in a 95-5 ratio in volume basis, and operated for over two HRTs (72 days). This greatly increased the COD of the feeding mixture, from an average of 41.5 g/L to 73.2 g/L (factor of 1.76), as well as the OLR, from an average of 1.66 g COD/L/day to 2.94 g COD/L/day. As seen in Figure 5.2, biogas production increased greatly, by an exceptional factor of 2.48, and its methane concentration did not decrease from 62-66% vol.

This increase in biogas production might be first considered as erroneous. Given that the inlet COD into the digester has increased by a factor of only 1.76, and biogas production has multiplied by 2.48. This overproduction of biogas is caused by two reasons: 1) The COD from ice cream waste has a higher biodegradability than SS (85.9% vs. 63.5%) and 2) co-digestion can enable synergies in

which the individual COD elimination of each co-substrate improves when co-digested. The COD removal has indeed increased from mono-digestion 48.2% to 66.8%, meaning that the additional COD from the ice cream is digested almost entirely and that SS digestion has also improved. VS removal increases from 47.0% to 63.5% compared to mono-digestion.

Figure 5.2 Co-digestion theoretical biogas production and measured biogas production

As it can be seen in Figure 5.2, the measured biogas production follows closely its theoretical value from the COD elimination, and the averaged value shows that 0.82 L/min are expected and 0.78 L/min are measured. The error is then reduced to a mere 5%. However, it is noticed how in the last month of experimentation a great error in the measured biogas production appears as its reading suddenly deviates without reason, and that error is also noticed in the subsequent co-digestion campaign with fruit waste. Due to these errors, the measured biogas production is no longer a trustworthy measure and biogas production will only be calculated from COD elimination. The unreliable measures could be attributed to biogas humidity condensing in the (thermal) mass flow meter.

5.3 Co-digestion campaign with fruit and vegetable waste

At the end of the ice-cream waste co-digestion campaign, the feeding pump malfunctioned and required spare parts, which took over two months to arrive and get install. The pilot plant was then re-inoculated with live SS from the on-site digester, and it was re-started but this time with a 95-5 volume mix of SS and fruits and vegetables waste and operated for 45 days before temperatures plummeted due to blockage in the heat exchanger. This residue, as seen in Section 3.3, is

characterized by its great fluctuation in properties. That fluctuation became apparent during the co-digestion campaign, with the waste shifting from being a mix of vegetables to solely tomatoes in the span of two weeks.

The feed COD rose from the mono-digestion campaign average of 41.5 g/L to an average of 50.93 g/L (factor of 1.23) and the OLR went from 1.66 g COD/L/day to 2.04 g COD/L/day. Fluctuations in the OLR and COD were much greater than those in the ice-cream waste co-digestion campaign, as both the SS and the co-substrate fluctuated. In Figure 5.3 the calculated biogas production and measured biogas production are presented; the latter can be discarded as the flow meter seemed to be malfunctioning. The calculated biogas production increased from the mono-digestion campaign average of 0.33 L/min to 0.56 L/min, which implies an increase factor of 1.70, again greater than the COD increase due to the higher biodegradability of the co-substrate (75% vs. 63.5%) and the co-digestion synergies.

Figure 5.3 Biogas production in the fruit waste co-digestion campaign

The COD elimination also increased from 48.2% to 59.2% and the VS removal increased from 47.0% to 51.8%.

6 Results scale-up

Once the co-digestion campaigns have validated the feasibility of using both co-substrates in Rincón de León WWTP, the full-scale implementation can be envisioned with the co-substrates availability and expected biogas production. Since the co-substrates availability is limited and can never reach the 5% volume recipe mix during the co-digestion campaigns, no inhibition is expected. See in Table 6.1 the expected outcomes of the full-scale implementation. The current full-scale in Rincón de León WWTP is based on a digesters' capacity of 10.000 m³, whereas the capacity of the pilot plant is of 1.6 m³. In terms of feeding rate it translates to 550 Tn/d for the full-scale scenario and 0.04 Tn/d for the pilot plant scenario.

Table 6.1 Full-scale co-digestion implementation considering the real waste production available

	Current scenario	Co-digestion with ice cream and fruit waste
SS feeding rate [Tn/day]	550	550
Ice cream waste feeding rate [Tn/day]	-	1.1
Fruit waste feeding rate [Tn/day]	-	1.9
Biogas production [Nm ³ /day]	5,000	15,565
Methane concentration [vol.%]	64%	64%
Biogas to CHP engine [Nm ³ /day]	2,993	3,558
Electricity production [MWh/y]	1,092	2,480
Extra electricity production [MWh/y]	-	394
Self-sufficiency electricity WWTP	9.3%	20.9%
Electricity price [€/MWh]	120	200
Extra electricity savings [€/y]	-	78,750
Waste management fee [€/t]	-	25
Waste management fee revenue [€/y]	-	27,400
Total revenue [€/y]	-	106,150
Carbon intensity mix Spain [Tn CO ₂ eq/MWh]*	0.217	0.217
Avoided CO ₂ emissions electricity [Tn CO ₂ eq./y]	-	86

*Source: Statista

Noticeably, the impact (energetic, economic and environmental) is limited due to the limited availability of ice cream waste and fruit waste. Self-sufficiency of electrical energy increases from 18.1% to 20.9% and the emission of 86 tons of CO₂ is avoided. It should be noted that the GHG

emissions of waste disposal nor transportation emissions have been taken into account, so the actual GHG emissions abatement might be greater than calculated for electricity self-consumption. However, the former must be evaluated with detailed co-substrate provider data, which is currently not available, whereas the latter can be estimated as done in Table 6.1.

Regarding the economic viability, due to the limited supply of co-substrates the savings are restricted to 78,750 € per year, and the waste management revenue is estimated to be 27,400 € per year with a waste management fee of 25 € per ton. The waste management business model must be further detailed, as it has a significant contribution to the total.

The same calculation was re-run considering that a 5% residue mix is possible, it being a 50-50 mixture of ice cream and fruit waste, the results are seen in Table 6.2. The potential economic, environmental and energetic impact is much higher, as the biogas production is twofold of the current method without co-digestion. Self-sufficiency climbs up to a staggering 36.8%. The increase in production is such that the CHP unit becomes the process bottleneck, as its maximum output is 500 kW electric, whereas from the potential biogas production of 10,450 Nm³/day it would be possible to have an output of 670 kW electric if the CHP unit was not limited to its maximal nominal output. If a new CHP unit was installed, then the electricity production could climb up even higher, as the CHP unit is old and performs poorly, with an estimated efficiency of 28-30%, whereas new biogas CHP units can have efficiencies up to >40%.

The estimated GHG savings because of energy self-sufficiency are 412 tons of CO₂ per year, without taking into account the avoided methane emissions from the current management of ice cream and fruit residues. The waste management revenue becomes even more significant due to the cap in biogas valorisation in the CHP unit. The total revenue taking into account waste management as well as energy savings exceeds 600,000 €, which makes it very attractive given the little changes to operation that would require such an implementation, limited mostly to a minor revamping of the centrifuges to account for the higher TS loads, higher flocculant and iron chloride expenditure and installing a line for co-substrate storage and feeding to the digesters.

The old CHP engine is potentially where the WWTP will have to evaluate either a moderate investment or a major overhaul to reach over 95% of operational availability and operation at 100% of its load. A new CHP unit with a capacity of 700 kWe would have a total installed CAPEX of 1-1.5 M€, an order of magnitude higher than the expected investment in centrifuges and the co-substrate line. Even accounting for the high range CAPEX of a new CHP engine, a simple payback period of 2-3 years is found, not considering slightly higher operational and maintenance costs aforementioned as well as of the engine higher load operation (engine oil, spare parts, etc.). It should be considered that in case of the CHP engine having a higher capacity than the current 500 kW, such as 700 kW, the electricity savings would climb up to 680,000 €/year and the total revenue would be of up to 950,000 €/year; this calculation does not take into account the higher efficiency of a potential new CHP unit, which could even increase estimates amounts by 30-40%.

The necessary amount of residues for the feeding of a 95/5 volume mix would be 14.5 tons per day for ice cream and 14.5 tons per day for fruit waste. This is an order of magnitude higher than the identified waste streams. Besides reaching out to similar industries in the area, it might be necessary to scout again for other types of organic residues and testing their BMP and co-digestion potential. It is also important to underline that although fruit waste and ice cream waste have been proven to be very good co-substrates, they have not been tested together due to lack of time, although there is no reason to expect negative cross-effects.

Table 6.2 Full-scale co-digestion implementation considering a hypothetical scenario where the required co-substrates volumes were available

	Current scenario	Co-digestion 95/5 volume mix
SS feeding rate [Tn/day]	550	550
Ice cream waste feeding rate [Tn/day]	-	14.5
Fruit waste feeding rate [Tn/day]	-	14.5
Biogas production [Nm ³ /day]	5,000	10,450
Methane concentration [vol.%]	64%	64%
Biogas to CHP engine [Nm ³ /day]	2,993	6,280
Extra biogas lost to flare [Nm ³ /day]	-	2,163
Electricity production [MWh/y]	1,092	4,378
Extra electricity production [MWh/y]	-	1,898
Self-sufficiency WWTP	9.3%	36.8%
Electricity price [€/MWh]	120	200
Extra electricity savings [€/y]	-	379,530
Waste management fee [€/Tn]	-	25
Waste management fee revenue [€/y]	-	264,150
Total revenue [€/y]	-	643,670
Carbon intensity mix Spain [Tn CO ₂ eq/MWh]*	0.217	0.217
Avoided CO ₂ emissions electricity [Tn CO ₂ eq./y]	-	412

*Source: Statista

7 Achieved impacts within B-WaterSmart

A set of SMART (specific, measurable, achievable, realistic, timely) targets were defined in the Grant Agreement, to monitor and quantify the expected impacts (EIs) and provide clear measures of the specific targets. Target values, shown in Table 8.1, based on the expertise and ambitions of the LL Leaders were defined towards the end of the project and to further expand beyond the end of the project, targeting 2040 as a time horizon.

Table 7.1 Quantitative target values of the LLs regarding defined indicators for EI 1 to EI 9 for different scales: **local**, **city**, **metropolitan**, **regional**; A: Alicante, B: Bodø, F: Flanders, L: Lisbon, E: EastFrisia, V: Venice

Impact No.	Expected Impact (EI) description	All numerical values are %																			
		A			B			F			L			E			V				
		initial	project end	in 2040	initial	project end	in 2040	initial	project end	in 2040	initial	project end	in 2040	initial	project end	in 2040	initial	project end	in 2040		
EI 1	Decrease in use of freshwater resources [freshwater abstracted / water supplied]		-10	-30						-2	-20		-20	-40		-2	-5				
EI 2	Improved water use efficiency [water supplied / population served]					-10	-30						-30	-30			-2	-10			
EI 3	Water reuse A [Treated wastewater used / water supplied]	30	40	71				<1	2	15		<2	5	15		1	2	5	4	50	>80
EI 4	Water reuse B [Treated ww. used / total ww. produced]	75	100	100				<1	2	10		<2	20	20		0	2	5	<1	30	>80
EI 5	Reduction in water-related energy use [of present use]		-25	-35									-30	-30							
EI 6	Energy recovery [of total potential in case]	5	30	40	0	80	90												<50	>90	>90
EI 7	Nutrient recovery [of total potential in case]	0	60	80								0	5	20		0	5	80	<50	>90	>90
EI 8	Mineral recovery [of total potential in case]	0	30	40				0	5	10											
EI 9	Recovery of other relevant resources a) salt; b) heat for de-icing	^a 0	^a 90	^a 90	^b 0	^b 20	^b 70														

The anaerobic co-digestion of sewage sludge and waste, defined as B-WaterSmart technology TP10, was selected with regard to a reduced use or maximum recovery of energy, which would partly address the Expected Impact 6 - Energy recovery. Also contributing to this EI in Alicante LL there is the microturbine for energy recovery from water streams described in Subtask 2.1.2. However, the microturbine was eventually installed in Monte Orgegia WWTP and will be addressed in D2.3.

A 5% was defined as the initial value of energy recovery in Rincón de León WWTP of the total potential considering the electricity consumption in the plant itself. This baseline value can vary along the years depending on not only the overall operation of the digesters and biogas systems but also in the energy consumption at the plant.

By the end of the project (August 2024) it was targeted for a 30% energy recovery. Even though the results obtained in the pilot plant are not representative considering a full-scale scenario, a couple of simulations have been carried out taking into account the improved biogas production up-scaled to the Rincón de León WWTP dimensions. In this sense, two potential scenarios could be drawn:

- Scenario A: taking as reference values in Table 6.1 where only the total waste produced from both cresam industry and fruit and vegetable industry is used for co-digestion. The waste availability can be the main limiting factor for the implementation of co-digestion at a full-scale level, given that the waste demand can be higher than the waste offer.

Scenario A	Result
RdL WWTP energy consumption in 2023 (MWh/y)	11,885
Energy produced through biogas (MWh/y)	2,480
EI 6 - Energy recovery (%)	20.9

- Scenario B: taking as reference values in Table 6.2 where a 95/5 volume mix is possible due to a hypothetical sufficient availability of waste. This scenario is being pursued currently in Alicante, where more potential waste producers are being searched for.

Scenario B	Result
RdL WWTP energy consumption in 2023 (MWh/y)	11,885
Energy produced through biogas (MWh/y)	4,378
EI 6 - Energy recovery (%)	36.8

On the other hand, when considering the year 2040 as a temporal benchmark, an alternative scenario can be simulated, given the ongoing plans for various interventions in the short term to enhance the overall biogas system at Rincón de León WWTP. These interventions encompass the revitalization of two additional currently inactive digesters, each with a capacity of 3,000 m³, the replacement of CHP units with more efficient alternatives, and the augmentation of installed capacity. Additionally, initiatives such as implementing pre-treatments to the sludge mix for enhanced hydrolysis and subsequently increased biogas yield are in the list of potential interventions.

In this particular simulation, the focus was exclusively on the expansion of digester capacity, which would see an increase from 10,000 m³ (in scenarios A&B) to 16,000 m³. Other parameters, such as plant consumption, CHP yield, CH₄ concentration, and more, were deliberately held constant to streamline the simulation process.

Scenario C	Result
RdL WWTP energy consumption in 2023 (MWh/y)	11,885
Digesters capacity (m ³)	16,000

Energy produced through biogas (MWh/y)	7,005
EI 6 - Energy recovery (%)	58.9

In summary, while the findings outlined in this section are derived from simulations extrapolated to the scaled-up dimension in Rincón de León WWTP, they unequivocally indicate that the practical execution of anaerobic co-digestion involving sewage sludge, ice-cream waste, and fruit and vegetable residues on a full scale would not only surpass but significantly exceed the targeted Expected Impacts. Projections suggest that by the conclusion of the project (>35%) and extending into 2040 (>50%), the observed positive outcomes would surpass the defined target values.

8 Specifications and technical requirements

For the successful implementation of the technology at future end users is essential to provide clear specifications and technical requirements. This section outlines the key parameters and standards that need to be met for a seamless integration of the technology, taking into account the results obtained within the work carried out at Alicante LL.

a) Specifications

Some of the specifications that have led to a successful piloting of the co-digestion technology in Rincón de León WWTP are summarised in the following table.

Table 8.1 Specifications for co-digestion implementation

Parameter	Requirement
Feedstock composition	
Organic content (%)	>60%
Moisture content (%)	70-80%
C/N ratio	20-40
Biodegradability of co-substrates (%)	>70%
System capacity	
Daily input capacity (tn/day)*	>3
Biogas production (m ³ /day)*	>10.500

*Some parameters will depend on the installed capacity of the WWTP. These numbers relate to a plant similar to Rincón de León WWTP.

b) Technical requirements

Table 9.2 gathers some of the technical requirements that, from the operational perspective during pilot testing in Rincón de León WWTP, might support other end users implementing the co-digestion technology in their facilities. It needs to be highlighted that these technical requirements are being suggested taking into account that this study has been executed by means of a pilot-scale plant that has not been connected to the whole biogas system in Rincón de León. This means that biogas produced in the pilot plant has not been valorised.

Table 8.2 Technical requirements for co-digestion implementation

Parameter	Requirement
Digestion System	
Reactor type	Anaerobic
Temperature range of reactor (°C)	35-55
Hydraulic Retention Time (days)	20-30
Mixing tank for substrates homogenization	
Supplementary equipments	Freezer to avoid pre-digestion
Pre-treatment of co-substrates*	Crusher
Biogas valorisation system	
Biogas pre-treatment for flow monitoring	Dehumidifier
CHP capacity (kW)	>500

*Pre-treatment of waste will depend on the substrate and its origin. In the specific case of Alicante LL a crusher was necessary to adapt the fruit waste from fruit and vegetables industry.

8.1. Waste management and handling

The Rincón de León WWTP produces sewage sludge during both the primary and secondary settling stages of the wastewater treatment process. These sludges are combined and sent to conventional anaerobic digesters for biogas production and stabilization. After digestion, the sludge undergoes thickening and dewatering using centrifuges, resulting in a product with approximately 20% dry matter. About 10% of this sludge is used in agricultural applications, while the remaining 90% is processed by the cement industry as an industrial symbiosis with a close industry. Prior to leaving the plant, the sludge is regularly monitored for key physicochemical properties (e.g., moisture content, pH, total and volatile solids, measured twice weekly) and heavy metal concentrations (e.g., cadmium, copper, nickel, measured biannually), with heavy metal monitoring being especially important for its agricultural use.

WWTP sludges are subject to the Spanish Law 7/2022 on waste and contaminated soils for a circular economy, which establishes the basic principles and rules for waste management. The specific regulation governing the use of treated sludge in agricultural soils is the Royal Decree (RD) 1310/1990. However, the maximum allowable heavy metal limits in materials and products applied

to agricultural soils or crops, as outlined in Annexes I A, I B, and I C, have recently been updated by Royal Decree 1051/2022 and are presented in Table 8.3

Table 8.3. Limit values for heavy metals allowed by Royal Decree 1051/2022 and results from the two analytical campaigns carried out in 2024.

Heavy metal	Limit value RD 1052/2022 (mg/Kg ms*)	Concentrations in July 2024	Concentrations in January 2024
Cadmium (Cd)	10	1.2	1.0
Copper (Cu)	1,000	287	285
Nickel (Ni)	300	67	41
Lead (Pb)	750	146	46
Zinc (Zn)	2,500	969	901
Mercury (Hg)	10	1.62	0.87
Hexavalent Chromium (Cr VI)	2	<2	<2
Inorganic arsenic (As)	40	<10	<10

*ms = dry matter

Historical analytical data from the Rincón de León WWTP show that heavy metal concentrations in sewage sludge have generally remained below the limits specified in Table 8.3, and in many cases, even below the detection thresholds. As a result, the sludge consistently complies with the regulatory limits established by legislation for its intended use.

In the context of B-WaterSmart, the co-digestion assessment was carried out in a parallel pilot-scale plant installed adjacent to the full-scale digesters. However, it was not integrated with the dewatering system (centrifuges) of the real plant and the resulting sludge, once co-digested, was directed to the drainage system and returned to the plant's headworks. Since this study was part of an innovation project (B-WaterSmart), the sludge produced with the pilot plant was not used for agricultural purposes, and heavy metal monitoring was excluded from the project's scope.

Nevertheless, the sewage sludge used in the pilot study was generated at the WWTP and was therefore indirectly monitored as part of the utility's routine operations, ensuring compliance with applicable regulations. In contrast, the co-substrates used in the study (i.e. ice cream waste and fruit and vegetable residues) were not analyzed for heavy metal content. However, it is important to note that the co-digestion mixture consisted of up to 5% co-substrate and 95% sewage sludge. Given the small proportion of co-substrate in the mixture, it is unlikely that any heavy metal content could

significantly raise concentrations above regulatory limits. For the same reason, we believe that such a low percentage of co-substrate would have minimal impact on key characteristics like the dewaterability of the final sludge product.

However, these topics are highly relevant for the implementation of the co-digestion technology at full scale. For this reason, we will tackle these issues in a new project that has been awarded to Cetaqua and Aguas de Alicante, the LIFE MERLIN project (LIFE23-CCM-ES-LIFE MERLIN 101158094). The LIFE MERLIN has the objective of further improving the biogas production process in anaerobic co-digestion by means of enzymatic hydrolysis pretreatment technologies. We will take this opportunity to take a close look into the resulting co-digested sludge, monitor potential pollutants that could hinder its final use and investigate possible significant changes in its quality as well as the implications.

9 Considerations in sludge pollution for agriculture

Sewage sludge, the inevitable byproduct of municipal WWTPs, presents a significant challenge for many countries due to its increasing volume and the environmental impacts associated with its disposal. According to the European Commission's 2010 report, 39% of sewage sludge produced in the European Union is recycled into agriculture, making it a critical element in the pursuit of circularity in waste management. However, the use of sludge in agriculture requires thorough waste characterization, as it often contains potentially harmful compounds, including heavy metals, organic pollutants, and emerging contaminants such as PFAS and pharmaceuticals. Without appropriate controls and monitoring, these substances can pose risks to ecosystems and human health, highlighting the need for technological advancements and updated regulatory frameworks to ensure safe sludge reuse.

Emerging pollutants in agricultural use of sewage sludge

The presence of persistent pollutants in sewage sludge poses a significant threat to its safe and sustainable reuse in agriculture. These include:

- **PFAS:** Widely used in industrial and consumer products, they are extremely resistant to degradation and can accumulate in soil and water.
- **Pharmaceuticals and Personal Care Products (PPCPs):** Introduced into the wastewater stream from households, hospitals, and industries, these substances can persist in the environment and disrupt ecosystems.
- **Heavy Metals:** Sludge can contain harmful metals like cadmium, lead, and mercury, which can accumulate in soil over time and pose risks to both plant growth and human health through the food chain.
- **Resistant Bacteria:** The spread of antibiotic-resistant bacteria is an emerging concern, as these microorganisms can survive sewage treatment processes and pose a threat to public health, particularly when sludge is applied to agricultural fields.

Despite growing concerns, many of these contaminants, including PFAS, organic micropollutants, and resistant bacteria, are not yet regulated in terms of their presence in sewage sludge for agricultural use. While heavy metals are regulated under the EU Sewage Sludge Directive (Council Directive 86/278/EEC of 12 June 1986), which sets limits to protect the environment, particularly soil, from heavy metal contamination, no similar legal limits or monitoring requirements currently exist for these emerging pollutants. This regulatory gap poses significant challenges in ensuring the safe application of sludge in agriculture.

In this sense, there is a growing call for regulatory bodies to address these pollutants within sludge management frameworks. Without formal monitoring or limits, there is a risk of long-term accumulation of these pollutants in soils, which could lead to contamination of crops and water resources, ultimately entering the food chain.

Technological gaps in pollutant removal

The challenge of removing persistent pollutants from wastewater and sludge lies in the limitations of current technologies. Despite some progress, the field of technology development for pollutant removal is still in its early stages, with most techniques at low maturity levels (TRLs).

Water treatment options: One potential approach would be to target the removal of PFAS and other micropollutants before secondary treatment in biological reactors, where high volumes of sludge are generated. However, the lack of efficient technologies capable of selectively removing these small compounds at this early stage of the wastewater treatment process is a significant barrier. At this point in the process, high concentrations of COD and suspended solids mainly make it difficult to isolate and remove these micropollutants efficiently. This is why this kind of compounds, when targeted, are addressed in tertiary or even quaternary treatments, when wastewaters have already a good quality and could already be discharged into the receiving body.

Sludge treatment options: The second approach focuses on treating the sludge itself after it is generated. In the case of heavy metals, for example, their removal from sewage sludge is still in an early stage of development, with most techniques still at the laboratory scale. Several methods have been proposed, divided into three main categories:

- Physical treatments: Techniques such as thermal treatment, adsorption, and electro dialysis are being explored.
- Chemical methods: Processes like coagulation and flocculation, acid or basic lixiviation, and ion exchange show potential but are far from being ready for large-scale applications.
- Biological treatments: Methods like the use of biosurfactants and biological lixiviation are under investigation for their potential to remove heavy metals in a more environmentally friendly way.

Some of these methods can be directly applied to sludge, while others require a two-step process. The first step often involves leaching, where heavy metals are transferred from the solid phase to the liquid phase. The second step focuses on removing the metals from the liquid phase using other separation techniques. Combining multiple approaches is generally recommended to improve the efficiency of heavy metal removal from sludge, but these technologies are not yet mature enough for widespread adoption.

Striking a balance between circularity and safety

Achieving circularity in wastewater and sludge management requires finding a balance between resource recovery and pollutant safety. Recycling sludge in agriculture fits within the principles of the circular economy, as it promotes the recycling of nutrients, and is promoted by the EU. However, contamination with emerging pollutants poses a serious risk to both environmental and human health.

To ensure the safety of using mixed sewage and (food) waste sludge in agriculture, it is critical to:

- **Expand monitoring:** Introduce mandatory testing for PFAS and other micropollutants in sewage sludge.
- **Refine regulatory frameworks:** Establish clear limits and guidelines for the safe use of sludge in agriculture, incorporating emerging pollutants into existing regulations.
- **Develop and scale up technologies:** Encourage investment in research and development for technologies capable of removing persistent pollutants, both at the early stages of water treatment and in the sludge treatment process.

Given the increasing concern of persistent pollutants in wastewater streams, regulatory bodies, industry stakeholders, and researchers must collaborate to address the existing gaps. This includes both updating regulations to reflect the presence of emerging contaminants and accelerating the development of treatment technologies. Only by addressing these pollution concerns can we ensure that co-digestion processes and sludge recycling align with circular economy principles, while safeguarding the environment and public health.

10 Conclusions

Two co-substrates, out of the four initially identified, showed potential (high COD, BMP and biodegradability): ice cream waste from cream industry and fruit waste from food unit. Oil&Fats from the supernatant of the WWTP were discarded due to low VS content and low availability.

Although the co-digestion pilot plant required a deep revamp and operation was interrupted several times due to mechanical problems with several pieces of equipment, the mono-digestion of sludge from the WWTP could be replicated successfully and the co-digestion of both co-substrates could be tested for a representative enough period of time: over two HRTs for ice cream waste (72 days) and almost 2 HRT for fruit waste (45 days).

The production of biogas was multiplied by 2.48 for ice cream waste and by 1.76 for fruit waste with a 5% volume mix with mixed sludge. This high productivity can be attributed to the high biodegradability of both co-substrates and to synergies in co-digestion, such as achieving a higher COD removal than if both co-substrates were mono-digested. No inhibition was observed.

Due to the low availability of co-substrates the energetic, economic and environmental impacts of full-scale implementation are limited. However, if higher quantities of similar co-substrates were to be fed into the digesters to replicate the tested 95/5 volume mix, the biogas generation would increase to the point of being able to run the CHP engine at full capacity and a significant part of biogas generation would require flaring. An investment in a new CHP unit is suggested, with a higher nominal capacity, as well as higher efficiency and operational availability with a 2-3 year estimated simple payback period. It is observed how a significant part of the revenue generated comes from waste management.

As next steps, it is recommended to further identify other potential co-substrates, similar to the successfully tested ones, to increase the total availability of organic residues in the area and maximise the positive impacts. Potential co-substrates could be wastes from the food-making sector such as brewery plants and confectionary industries. It is also recommended to further study the economic implications and business model of waste management.

In terms of Expected Impact within B-WaterSmart anaerobic co-digestion technology TP10 has demonstrated a maximized energy recovery from sewage sludge and other wastes. The results obtained for the different scenarios point out a progressive increase in energy recovery, surpassing the initial baseline of 5% to achieve a targeted 30% by the project's conclusion in 2024. Furthermore, projections extending to 2040 suggest a substantial surpassing of the defined target values, with an expected energy recovery exceeding 50%.

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